

TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' USE OF STRATEGIC COMPETENCE IN ORAL INTERACTION

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Abstract: The article analyzes the concept of strategic competence in aspect of the problem developed by the author of teaching foreign language communicative activities. The competence-based approach is recognized as the leading approach in the training of specialists of any profile. The presence of such professional competencies as a specialist's possession of the ability to communication in oral and written forms in English for solving problems of professional communication, interpersonal and intercultural interaction are decisive in the selection of candidates for position. The content characteristics of the sought-for concept are described, through the prism of which it is proposed author's definition of strategic competence and its component composition.

Keywords: strategic competence, communicative activity, communicative strategies, components of competence, general skills of strategic competence.

Due to the fact that main goal of higher professional education is to develop the ability of students to communicate orally in foreign languages for solving problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction. Higher education is designed to provide a graduate with a complex general cultural and professional competencies in the composition of which stands out, in particular skills such as the ability to be logically correct, reasoned and clearly build oral and written speech; ability to written and oral communication in the native language, skills of the culture of social and business communication in foreign languages [7].

A strategic competence is a type of behavior of a communicant in a communication situation, "which is conditioned and correlated with a plan for achieving communicative goals within the framework of a typical frame scenario of functional-semantic representations" [2]. The study of the strategies of communicative behavior of representatives of the English-speaking society, their linguistic-sociopsychological and cultural characteristics contributes to the introduction of "non-native speakers" of the language to the value orientations of the speakers of the given language, the convergence of the intercultural distance between representatives of different societies, and, ultimately, the formation of a linguistic personality, who owns the basics of intercultural communication, and its upbringing, readiness to adapt to the culture of another people, a different socio-cultural context of interaction and influence in order to develop an optimal communication strategy in a foreign language [4].

The use of compensatory strategies when communicating in their native language indicates a high probability that learners will have to use them in the target language in order to solve problems that may arise during communication. It is important that they understand that there is nothing wrong with using these strategies, especially in open-ended assignments, and that they will help to cope with group and non-classroom situations for which the trainees were not prepared.

Analysis of the latest research and publications that the issue of component of composition of the communicative competence and in the place in its strategic component (I.V. Aleshanova and N.A.Frolova [8], E.V. Krasilnikova, T.A. Sokolova, N.I. Tsvetkova [1] and others), revealing a lack of unanimity in the interpretation of this term, as well as a large number of opinions regarding the content and area of functioning of strategic competence (L.A. Kareva, T.A. Tolmacheva, Yu.A. Molchanova [2,3]).

The purpose of this article is to analyze some of the existing points of view on the concept of communicative activities in the aspect of foreign language training of students of university, paying special attention to communicative competence and the functioning of its strategic component. This is the activity of applying communicative competence in the process of perception and / or pedagogical science in order to solve the communicative task of communication in a certain field of activity [1].

One of basic components is the strategic competence, which the British linguists M. Kanel and M. Swain defined as a set of verbal and non-verbal communicative strategies used in cases where certain difficulties arise in communication or a rupture threatens [6]. A. N. Shamov is in solidarity with this point of view. He emphasizes that strategic competence is the ability to use verbal and non-verbal means (strategies) to which the person resorts if the communication do not take place (re-ask, request for a new word, re-reading a phrase, an incomprehensible place in the text, the use of gestures, facial expressions, etc.) [7]. A similar interpretation is also adhered to by N.D Galskova, who understands strategic competence as the ability to compensate the lack of knowledge of the language, speech and communication [4].

M.V. Daver believes that strategic competence is the ability to develop programs and plans as efficiently as possible, with the point of view of the doer, performance [2]. Obviously, in this sense, strategic competence exists as part of any subject and professional competence, and should come into effect when there is a need to search solutions for real or perceived problems in the course of communicative or educational activities [2,6].

T.I. Timofeeva believes that the presence of students' strategic competence is necessary in order to feel more confident in contacts with an interlocutor, including a foreign language, because this competence provides the ability to solve problems with using verbal and non-verbal funds. Thus, it also recognizes the strategic component as one of the main components communicative competence and believes that it is "determines communication" [3]. It is obvious that the presence of strategic competence in trainees is necessary in order to feel more confident in contacts with an interlocutor, including a foreign language, when reading a foreign language text, because this competence ensures the ability to solve problems of various kinds using verbal and non-verbal means. Therefore, it is advisable to highlight strategic competence as a separate component.

The study of a foreign language is aimed at achieving the main goal: the development of foreign language communicative competence in the aggregate of its components - speech, linguistic, sociocultural, compensatory, educational and cognitive [8]. In this case, the compensatory competence (or strategic) is understood as the ability to find a way out of a situation in the face of a shortage of language resources when receiving and transmitting information. Strategic competence is interpreted as the ability to select and use the most effective strategies for solving various communication problems and presupposes possession of such general skills like:

- draw up a plan for the implementation of a specific communication task;
- to fulfill this plan at the level of the statement;
- assess the degree of achievement of communicative communication to improve communication in the future;
- ability and willingness to take risks in communication situations to compensate for missing knowledge or abilities;
- use effective general teaching skills;
- ask clarifying questions.

The above understanding strategic competence allows us to believe that it acts at all levels that make up the communicative competence: linguistic, sociolinguistic, social, discursive. The implementation of the considered components in strategic competence. The cognitive component of competence, as it was stated above, contains knowledge of the content and purpose for communication activities, methods of obtaining and constructing new knowledge; in relation to strategic competence, it gives an idea of communicative competence as the most important general cultural competence, the place of strategic competence as its basic component, and also includes information about basic communication strategies, it is used in situations of everyday and professional communication.

In conclusion, having considered the essence of the concept of “strategic competence”, we propose the following definition of this competence: strategic competence is the most important component of the communicative competence, acting at all its levels and taking into account the cognitive, activity, motivational and personal components; it is formed the ability of an individual to successfully solve problems arising in the process of performing a certain communicative task. One of the significant characteristics of the foreign language preparation of students of university for successful intercultural communication is the formation of strategic competence. In order to for effective intercultural communication activities to be possible, strategic competence must be acquired for student and graduate of university is functional in nature. In our opinion, this is a promising direction in the study of this problem.

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